

TECHNOLOGICAL COMFORT ZONE: THE EVOLUTION OF HUMAN ADAPTATION AND COMPLACENCY

Stefan Zweig emphasizes the profound impact of the telegraph on human history in one of his famous books^[1]:

"We later generations will never comprehend the astonishment of the early generation at the first successful results of the electric telegraph. The astonishment was immeasurable when the tiny electrical spark ... whose existence was barely perceptible until yesterday ... suddenly acquired a diabolical power that could cross countries, mountains, and continents. It was impossible not to marvel that an unfinished thought, a word whose ink had not yet dried, could be simultaneously recorded, read, and understood thousands of miles away. The invisible current flickering between the two poles of the tiny voltaic piles could travel across the entire planet from one end to the other. Mankind was amazed that this toy-like device, which only yesterday in the physics laboratory could attract paper particles by friction with glass, could be developed to a potential millions and billions of times greater than human muscle strength and speed. Like Ariel, it could transmit news, move trains, and illuminate roads and houses, just by passing through the air, invisible to the eye. For the first time since the world began, the relationship between time and space was so radically altered by this discovery."

In the following decades, humanity experienced similar astonishment with the advent of the telephone, followed by the development of radio, television, fax machines, and, in the last quarter century, the Internet. Although these advancements, each pushing the boundaries of communication, initially garnered admiration, humanity quickly adapted to these technologies. Each of these disruptive technologies succeeded in rapidly supplanting their predecessors, which had previously held significant historical impact.

Today, information and communication technologies have advanced to such an extent that no one questions where mass information is stored globally or how it can be transferred so quickly when needed. Similarly, no one ponders how voice, image, or information can spread so swiftly on social networks. The likely reason for this is that human beings have accepted the acceleration of communication and easy access to information as integral parts of their lives.

Even artificial intelligence, the latest development that has managed to surprise humanity in recent years, is now becoming a part of people's daily lives faster than expected. Though it has not yet reached its golden age, the limited benefits offered by artificial intelligence in its infancy have already captivated humanity.

As such, apart from a handful of researchers, futurists, and conspiracy theorists, few are concerned about the problems that the rapid development of artificial intelligence may cause. This is one of the primary issues that should be addressed and studied seriously. Because human beings, who no longer feel the need to step out of the technological comfort zone offered by today's technology, do not yet recognize that this situation may pose serious dangers for a sustainable future.

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REFERENCES

[1] Zweig, S. (1964). *Sternstunden der Menschheit. Vierzehn historische Miniaturen*. Fischer Taschenbuch Verlag, Frankfurt am Main.